

THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STRENGTH QUALITIES IN FOOTBALL PLAYERS 15-17 YEARS OLD

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Abstract. Football in the modern world is one of the most popular sports, which is enjoyed by people belonging to different age categories and levels of physical fitness. But, for obvious reasons, high demands are placed on professional players, namely on their physical development. This is due to the need to perform exercises with the ball and exercises without the ball in short time intervals.

Keywords: Football player, strength, stability, technology, method, sport.

INTRODUCTION

It is necessary to completely exclude monotonous, unidirectional activities from the training set, as they kill the gaming activity in the athlete.

Jump in the fight for the riding ball; powerful head blow; impact force and supporting leg strength; the strength of the arms, when they have to spring back to take the weight of the body after a header in a fall, are just some of the main aspects of the use of force in football. In addition, it is imperative for a football player to engage in athletics to develop aerobic endurance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Strength is the ability to overcome external resistance or stress(es) [3].

One of the most important physical qualities of a person is strength ability. They mean the ability, through muscle tension, to overcome mechanical forces that interfere with the performance of a motor action, to counteract these external forces and perform the necessary locomotion, i.e. show "strength" [2].

Strength capabilities are fully manifested through any motor activity. Their manifestation is influenced by various factors, the significance of which in each individual case varies depending on the specificity of motor actions, the conditions of their manifestation, the type of strength abilities, age, and gender characteristics of the trainee [1].

The leading tasks in developing strength abilities are:

1. Ensure the full development of strength in all muscle groups by influencing them with adequate strength exercises. Solving this problem allows you to form the musculoskeletal system.

2. To ensure, within the framework of physical education, the diversified development of all manifestations of strength abilities (actual strength, speed-strength, strength endurance) and maintain the developing and formative effect for as long as possible.

3. Ensure maximum manifestation of strength abilities within the framework of professional, applied and sports activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When developing strength qualities, use such exercise options as:

1. Exercises with external weights. This group includes exercises that involve an additional load that increases your own body weight. These include the weight of other objects, external resistance from a partner, or another force. Here, exercises with strictly dosed weights (weight of equipment, equipment) are distinguished. It should be noted that exercises of this plan have taken a dominant place among strength training means. As a rule, the weights here vary in the range of 50-60% of the individual maximum weight.

There are also exercises with loosely dosed external weights. Most often this happens when a partner acts as a counteraction, whose external resistance does not depend on the practitioner. As a rule, such exercises are used to improve strength motor actions.

2. Exercises with self-weights. This group includes exercises with your own weight, motor actions in self-resistance. The weight here is created due to the gravity forces of various parts of the body. As a rule, these are gymnastics exercises performed at a slow pace. It is noteworthy that exercises of this type are available to most practitioners and do not require special equipment. Self-resistance exercises stand out here as a separate group. Their original term was "volitional gymnastics." The essence of performing these exercises is to hold static poses for a long time, caused by antagonist muscles, as well as in a combination of static, dynamic, inferior mode of muscle work.

The essence of developing actual strength abilities using near-maximum and maximum weights is:

- in the overcoming mode of muscle work;
- in an inferior mode of muscle work.

The development of actual strength capabilities is associated with exercises that use weights with a weight equal to 90-95% of the maximum. Rest intervals - until complete recovery, around 4-5 minutes [4].

Football training regimens often use four basic methods that vary the intensity of the workout:

- 1) increasing the weight of the equipment used in each exercise;
- 2) increasing the number of repetitions with a selected weight in each exercise;
- 3) maintaining the weight of the equipment, the number of approaches and repetitions in each exercise, reducing rest intervals between approaches;
- 4) increasing the number of approaches to each exercise.

CONCLUSION

In a number of sports, including football, the methodology for developing strength qualities needs further improvement. According to a number of studies, young football players are significantly inferior in the level of strength training to representatives of other sports. It is especially important to significantly increase the level of strength training of young football players at the age at which the foundation of their sports skills is laid, in particular, attention should be paid to middle school age - the age of formation of all basic life support systems and their improvement.

In this regard, research devoted to the analysis of the development of motor qualities in adolescents, as well as the development of differentiated methods for the development of motor qualities of young football players, are relevant areas in the theory and methodology of physical education and sports training.

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